

Adsorption of Organic Acids on Low Carbon Steel

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The adsorption from solution of chloroacetic acid on low carbon steel has been measured using Langmuir and Bockris-Swinkels isotherm. The coverage has been determined and the standard free energy of adsorption about 4 kJ/mol. the adsorption arises largely from metal-adsorbate dispersion interaction differences between water and organic acid. A knowledge on the adsorption of organic acids at the electrode-solution interface is needed for understanding of organic electrode reactions and the inhibitive action of organic acid on corrosion.

Adsorption of chloroacetic acids on low carbon steel electrode is studied in order to find the type of adsorption isotherm which best explains the experimental data. The degree of surface coverage of low carbon steel with chloroacetic acid solutions was calculated from its effect on the rate of corrosion. This technique is commonly used in adsorption studies¹.

Results and Discussion

The results of immersion in 10^{-5} – 10^{-1} M of mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acids showed that the weight-loss increases linearly with time.

From Table 1, it can be seen that the corrosion rates in the solutions of different acids and at different pH values are markedly increased by dilution. However, the corrosion rate of low carbon steel in chloroacetic acid solutions at different pH values reaches a minimum in 10^{-1} M at pH 4 for

Table 1 (Contd.)

		Concentration 0.01 M			
1	1	5.023	2.031	0.711	
	2	4.800	1.220	0.653	
	3	4.500	0.975	0.593	
	4	2.900	0.311	0.549	
2	1	—	1.921	—	
	2	—	1.155	—	
	3	—	1.032	—	
	4	—	0.332	—	
3	1	—	—	0.785	
	2	—	—	0.685	
	3	4.800	—	0.603	
	4	3.100	—	0.513	
4	1	7.500	2.153	0.854	
	2	5.000	1.335	0.721	
	3	4.900	0.985	0.712	
	4	3.300	0.415	0.479	
7	1	5.900	2.341	0.912	
	2	5.600	1.293	0.785	
	3	9.400	1.213	0.633	
	4	5.300	0.310	0.495	
		Concentration 0.00001 M			
1	1	—	2.334	0.781	
	2	5.000	2.115	0.675	
	3	4.500	1.583	0.615	
	4	—	0.613	0.472	
2	1	6.200	—	—	
	3	6.500	2.453	0.879	
	2	—	2.183	0.712	
	3	—	1.731	0.675	
4	1	—	0.321	0.493	
	2	3.020	—	—	
	1	—	2.731	0.913	
	2	5.300	2.543	0.712	
3	3	4.700	1.632	0.675	
	4	3.550	0.459	0.589	
	5	2	5.900	—	—
	3	5.000	—	—	
6	1	6.700	—	—	
	4	4.030	—	—	
	7	1	6.800	2.635	0.993
		2	6.700	2.293	0.895
3		5.600	1.991	0.732	
4		—	0.693	0.694	

TABLE 1—CORROSION RATE OF LOW CARBON STEEL IN MONO-, DI- AND TRICHLOROACETIC ACID SOLUTIONS AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Time day	pH	$\times 10^{-4}$ Corrosion rate (mg/cm ² /day)		
		Monochloro	Dichloro	Trichloro
Concentration 0.1 M				
1	1	4.78	1.632	0.811
	2	4.30	1.132	0.611
	3	4.10	1.032	0.584
	4	2.20	0.533	0.432
3	1	—	1.772	0.692
	2	—	1.453	0.632
	3	—	1.339	0.593
	4	—	0.325	0.495
4	1	4.012	1.850	0.722
	2	3.800	—	0.675
	3	4.000	1.551	0.622
	4	2.900	0.367	0.522
5	1	4.930	—	—
	2	4.800	1.723	—
	3	—	—	—
	4	—	—	—
7	1	5.100	1.993	0.792
	2	4.900	1.532	0.699
	3	4.800	1.223	0.578
	4	3.500	0.578	0.463

all the acid solutions. The change of corrosion rate with concentration is greater in mono-, than di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions and at pH 1 than pH 4 (Figs. 1–3). The decrease in the corrosion

Fig. 1. Corrosion rate for steel in 0.00001 M trichloroacetic acid at pH range 1-4.

Fig. 2. Corrosion rate for steel in 0.00001 M dichloroacetic acid at pH range 1-4.

Fig. 3. Corrosion rate for steel in 0.00001 M monochloroacetic acid at pH range 1-4.

rate with increase in acid concentration suggests that mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions act as anodic inhibitors for low carbon steel electrode. The inhibitive function of these acids may be associated with their ability to become adsorbed on the steel surface and thus retards the entry of Fe²⁺ ions into the solution at the anodes. Two alternative reactions are possible at the anode, dissolution of Fe²⁺ ions or the formation of a salt to seal the uncovered points in the salt layer formed.

A Langmuir adsorption model with adsorption only on anodic site may account for the increase in inhibition with increase in acid concentration.

$$\text{If } \frac{\text{inhibited corrosion rate}}{\text{uninhibited corrosion rate}} = W_i/W_u \quad (1)$$

where W_i is the weight-loss in inhibited solution and W_u the weight-loss in 10⁻⁵ M chloroacetic acid solutions. If the adsorption follows the simple Langmuir model then

$$\theta/(1-\theta) = AC \exp(Q_a/RT) \quad (2)$$

where A is a constant, C the concentration of inhibitor and Q_a is the heat of adsorption for mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions and at different pH values (1-4). Thus

$$\log \theta/(1-\theta) = \log A + \log C + Q_a/2.303 RT \quad (3)$$

To test the conformity of the results with this simple model, $\log \theta/(1-\theta)$ was plotted against $\log C$, which should give a straight line with unit gradient for all pH values, for mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions (curves are not shown). However, the gradient is much less than unity (0.23, 0.19, 0.16 and 0.15) for mono-, (0.18, 0.16, 0.14 and 0.12) for di-, and (0.15, 0.13, 0.12 and 0.10) for trichloroacetic acids at pH values 1-4 respectively. Graham² pointed out that the Langmuir constant K (slope of the straight line, which he named the equilibrium function) can possibly be less than unity for adsorption on heterogeneous surface in general and much smaller than unity when there is no lateral interaction between the adsorbate molecules. It has frequently been shown^{3,4} that the

adsorption of anions (aggressive or inhibitive) may control the corrosion process.

Degree of coverage : The degree of coverage (θ) is given by

$$\theta = 1 - W_i/W_a \quad (4)$$

where W_i and W_a are the weight-loss in inhibitive (high concentration) and corrosive (low concentration, $10^{-5} M$) of the tested acids at different pH values from 1 to 4 respectively. The degree of coverage (θ) increases with concentration as shown in Table 2. As the concentration of the organic acids increases, θ approaches unity which corresponds to the adsorption of a complete monolayer on the electrode surface.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF θ WITH CONCENTRATION OF MONO-, DI- and TRICHLOROACETIC ACIDS AND pH VALUES

[Acid] M	pH			
	1	2	3	4
Monochloro				
1 × 3	0.132	0.188	0.229	0.291
1 × 2	0.180	0.161	0.218	0.280
1 × 1	0.127	0.138	0.189	0.250
1 × 10 ⁻¹	0.06	0.107	0.162	0.222
1 × 10 ⁻²	0.047	0.085	0.159	0.205
1 × 10 ⁻³	0.029	0.047	0.075	0.116
Dichloro				
1 × 2	0.371	0.394	0.450	0.766
1 × 1	0.327	0.343	0.396	0.640
1 × 10 ⁻¹	0.261	0.296	0.292	0.518
1 × 10 ⁻²	0.187	0.257	0.247	0.383
1 × 10 ⁻³	0.073	0.218	0.198	0.050
Trichloro				
1 × 2	0.410	0.430	0.460	0.740
1 × 1	0.370	0.400	0.410	0.618
1 × 10 ⁻¹	0.200	0.219	0.210	0.332
1 × 10 ⁻²	0.080	0.122	0.134	0.286
1 × 10 ⁻³	0.060	0.100	0.150	0.200

In order to test the applicability of the Bockris-Swinkels isotherm,

$$\theta [\theta + x(1-\theta)^{x-1}] / (1-\theta)^x \cdot x^x = (C/55.5) \exp. (-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ} / RT) \quad (5)$$

where ΔG_{ads}° is the standard free energy of adsorption. Equation (5) was computed for $x=1, 2, 3$, etc., using the experimental values of θ . The left-hand-side of equation (5) was then plotted against concentration either (a) on linear scales where the correct values of x give straight line passing through the origin or (b) on logarithmic scales where a straight line of unit slope indicates the correct x value. Fig. 4 shows a plot of left-hand-side of equation (5) versus concentrations of the organic acids on logarithmic scales for various values of x , and the slopes of the straight lines are shown in Table 3. The correct values of x turned out to be unity. Thus, one water molecule is displaced by each organic acid molecule. It has been suggested by Damaskin^{6, 9} that the group of associated water

Fig. 4. Test of the Bockris-Swinkels values of x are given on the straight lines for dichloroacetic acid solution at pH=4.

molecules is displaced off the surface as a result of substitutional adsorption. There is some evidence that at room temperature, water forms groups of five molecules in a tetrahedral arrangement⁷. When such a tetrahedron adsorbs on a metal surface, it is obvious that its base, i.e. three water molecules, would face the metal surface. The central molecule would be at a longer distance from the electrode surface than the base molecules. The area occupied by each water group would thus be about equal to the area occupied by one water molecule. This seems to be a possible explanation of the above finding. However, Dhar *et al.*⁸ argued that the association of water in three to four hydrogen bonded units finds no basis in current theories of water structure. Along with this objection it may be added that if one accepts the view that water exists in tetrahedral units in the bulk of solution, it is not clear whether these tetrahedra could retain their structure at an electrode-electrolyte interface where there is a large potential gradient across the double layer; a condition which favours the adsorption of water in the immediate vicinity of the electrode as single molecules orientated in the direction of the potential gradient.

The standard free energy change, as defined by equation (5), can be calculated from the data for various values of x and 0. It is seen that for

$x=2-4$, $-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}$ increases with increasing coverage and only at $x=1$, it is independent of coverage. It is obvious that the use of incorrect values of x results in dependence of the calculated $-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}$ on coverage as pointed out before by Dhar *et al.*⁸. As shown above, the correct value of x for organic acids is one, hence the standard free energy of adsorption of the organic acids ($-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}$) on low carbon steel surface is about 4 kJ mol^{-1} .

TABLE 3—DEPENDENCE OF ΔG_{ads}° ON THE RATIO OF x AND pH OF THE ACID

Acid	pH	θ	$-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}$ (kJ mol^{-1}) Bockris-Swinkles equation (6)			
			$x=1$	2	3	4
Dichloro-acetic	1	0.261	Slope=1	0.5	0.4	0.3
			$-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}=1$	1.9	1.99	2.1
	4	0.518	$x=1$	2	3	4
			Slope=1	5.4	13.6	46
			$-\Delta G_{ads}^{\circ}=1$	7.7	12.4	17.9

According to Le Chatelier principle⁹, chloroacetic acids dissociate in presence of perchloric acid as a buffer for adjusting the pH values at equilibrium as

At $\text{pH}=1$, the reaction will shift to the left (influence of common ion H^+ on dissociation of XCH_2COOH in presence of perchloric acid) and thus adsorption becomes small; as the H^+ ion concentration decreases, and the pH of solution will rise and shift the reaction to the right, resulting in more of adsorption of the anion.

The potential of zero charge (PZC) of iron in acid medium is about -370 mV^{10} . Thus, the potential range over which the degree of coverage is constant is -300 to -500 mV (SCE) according to the type of chloroacetic acids and pH values, extending on both sides of PZC. At positive potentials compared to PZC, adsorption is due to electrostatic attraction between the electrode surface which acquires a positive charge and the carboxylic group. At a negative potential compared to the PZC where the electrode surface acquires a negative charge, adsorption may be attributed also to electrostatic attraction between the electrode surface and the protonated molecule because the electronic pair which connects carbon atom of the CH_2Cl group with the carbon atom of carboxylic group, is somewhat displaced towards chlorine atom. Such displacement leads to the displacement of electrons

which connect the carboxylic carbon atom with oxygen atom and as a result the hydrogen atom will have a positive charge due to the higher electronegativity of chlorine atom.

Experimental

Low carbon steel specimens (C, 0.05%) were standardised at $20 \times 50 \text{ mm}$, the total surface area exposed to attack therefore being 20 cm^2 . Degreasing was carried out by immersing the specimens in a mixture of acetone, alcohol and benzene and then swabbing the same mixture. The surface was rubbed with filter paper, then with a piece of silk and the specimens finally stored in a desiccator. They were weighed immediately before being placed in mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions and then totally immersed in 100 ml of testing medium of mono-, di- and trichloroacetic acid solutions at different concentrations and different pH values ranging from 1 to 4, which remained in a quiescent state throughout the period of the test lasting over several days. The pH of the solutions was adjusted by adding small amount of sodium hydroxide or perchloric acid. All reagents were of analytical grade. The test solution was not renewed during the period. The experiment was conducted at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

At the end of the experiments, the corrosion products were removed by immersing the specimens in a solution of 10% H_2SO_4 containing 0.1% thio-urea, and swabbing with the same solution. The specimens were then rinsed with distilled water, alcohol and ether, dried and reweighed.

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